

Standard Operating Procedure

Title: Sieving procedure for the fractionation of microplastic sized powders

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1. Scope and application

This standard operating procedure (SOP) has been developed to fractionate microplastics (1-1000 μm , ISO/TR 21960:2020) [1] via a sieve cascade with mesh sizes of 500, 100 and 50 μm . The samples are plastic particles in powder form. Plastic particles were able to pass a certain mesh size, stayed between sieves of two mesh sizes or were not able to pass a sieve with a certain mesh size. The SOP is specifically designed for dry sieving.

2. Terms, definitions and normative references

(1) “*plastic*”

material which contains as an essential ingredient a high polymer (3.1) and which, at some stage in its processing into finished products, can be shaped by flow

Note 1 to entry: Plastics consists mainly polymers and minor contents of additives (3.7).

Note 2 to entry: Supplementary to the term “plastic”, “plastic product” is also used. According to ISO 472, a plastic product represents “any material or combination of materials, semi-finished or finished product that is within the scope of ISO/TC 61, Plastics”.

Note 3 to entry: Plastics comprise both thermoplastic (3.3) and thermoset (3.4) materials.” [1]

(2) “*microplastic*”

any solid plastic particle insoluble in water with any dimension between 1 μm and 1000 μm (=1 mm)

Note 1 to entry: This term relates to plastic materials within the scope of ISO/TC 61. Rubber, fibers, cosmetic means, etc. are not within the scope.

Note 2 to entry: Typically, a microplastic object represents a particle intentionally added to end-user products, such as cosmetic means, coatings, paints, etc. A microplastic object can also result as a fragment of the respective article.

Note 3 to entry: Microplastics may show various shapes.

Note 4 to entry: The defined dimension is related to the longest distance of the particle”. [1]

3. Abbreviated terms

[SOP] – Standard operating procedure

[PSD] – Particle size distribution

4. Method principle

This SOP is a general guide through sieving procedure with instrument Retsch™ sieve shakers AS 200 Control (Fisher scientific). The instrument is characterized by digital setting for frequently repeated sieving operations under the same conditions.

5. Safety procedures and precautions

Standard safety operating procedures including those of the local labs have to be followed at all times. Special care has to be taken to avoid health risks, while working with small microplastics. Microplastics smaller than 40 µm can be air driven. Microplastics smaller than 10 µm can be inhaled.

6. Procedure

6.1 Apparatus and equipment

This section is listing and specifying all equipment used in the procedure:

- Metal spatula
- 100 mL Flask
- Retsch™ sieve shakers AS 200 Control
- Sonorex Super RK 514 H
- Container for collection of the particles < 50 µm
- Lid to place on top of the sieve stack
- Stainless steel sieves with mesh sizes of 500, 100 and 50 µm
- Drying oven

6.2 Chemicals, reference materials and reagents

- Microplastic sample
- Milli-Q water
- Isopropanol
- Ethanol

6.3 Sample

This section lists the nature of the samples and the amount of sample that is being processed.

In principle, all solid microplastic samples can be fractionated. The amount of microplastic sample should not exceed the capacity of the sieves during the fragmentation process due to possible particles aggregation or clogged meshes. Approximately 88 cm³ (e.g. 40 g of polypropylene) of microplastic sample is the maximum quantity allowed for efficient sieving with the mesh used.

6.4 Equipment preparation

To avoid contamination, work as clean as possible, especially plastic-free.

All the meshes should be carefully cleaned before the sieving. Each mesh has been washed first with ethanol. Mesh should be held vertically to avoid a direct jet on it which could ruin or even break it. Afterwards, each mesh has been inserted horizontally in the ultrasound bath (e.g. Sonorex Super RK 514 H) containing deionized water from ten to fifteen minutes to remove the remaining particles and later placed in the oven at 80°C until completely drying. A washing with ethanol before the oven can speed up drying times.

The microplastic sample should be stored plastic free (e.g. in a cleaned glass flask)

6.5 Measurement description

1. Stack all the meshes starting with the final container for particle < 50 µm collection. Please on top 50, 100, and 500 µm. The last will be the largest size;
2. Put the microplastic sample on top of the sieve with the biggest mesh size;
3. Place the lid to close the sieve stack and insert the sieve stack into the Retsch™ sieve shakers AS 200 Control;
4. Lock the sieves by pressing the levers on the sides of the instrument so that the sieves cannot move during the shaking motion;
5. Set the parameters. For plastic polymers, the following parameters have been used exemplarily twice:
 - Time (min): 10
 - Amplitude (mm/g): 1.40

- Interval time (s): 0.5
- 6. Once the shaking motion is completed, press the side levers again and push upwards to remove the sieves;
- 7. Collect in different glass flasks the plastic powder sieved for the different fractions separately (If you want to know the particle mass per size fraction, weigh the glass flask before and after filling). Use a clean metal spatula for help;
- 8. Clean the sieves using the same method described in the paragraph 6.4.

Figure 1 Retsch™ sieve shakers AS 200 Control

7. Calculation of results

Mass of plastic powder per size fraction can be easily determined by weighing the glass flask before and after filling with the individual size fractions.

$$m (\text{filled glass}) - m (\text{empty glass}) = m (\text{plastic powder for the individual size fraction})$$

8. Quality control

The particle size of the individual fractions can be measured by laser diffraction.

9. Measurement uncertainty and traceability

It is important to not overload the sieves by usage of too much starting material. This will lead to agglomeration and less size separation. Smaller particles will be found in sieves with higher mesh size.

10. Reporting of results

Mesh size (μm)	Mass (g)	Particle size distribution (D_{50}) (μm) - Dry dispersion	Particle size distribution (D_{50}) (μm) - Wet dispersion
> 500	7	320.9 ± 3.1	397.4 ± 3.3
500- 100	28.5	263 ± 6.0	296.6 ± 35.3
100-50	0.60	116.2 ± 0.1	115.6 ± 0.2
< 50	0.03	48.4 ± 0.1	57.0 ± 1.0
Total mass weighed	36.13		
Mass loss	3.87		
Percentage mass loss (%)	9.7		

Table 1 Mass and particle size distribution (PSD) from the sieving of 40 g of polypropylene (PP)

The results in terms of mass (g) and particle size distribution (PSD) (μm) from the sieving of polypropylene (40 g) are shown in Table 1. The PSD has been done via laser diffraction and expressed through D_{50} , which represents the measured volume below 50% of the particles are. The HELOS/BR+RODOS/L+ASPIROS dry dispersion and the HELOS/BR+CUVETTE wet dispersion has been applied obtaining comparable values for the different size ranges. During sieving, some plastic particles may become trapped between two sieves of different mesh sizes or may fail to pass through the sieve, remaining in the larger fraction. If a particle is elongated, with one of its dimensions smaller than the mesh size, it may pass through even if its other dimension exceeds the mesh size. Additionally, larger particles tend to have a higher electrostatic charge, which makes separation more difficult and leads to the formation of aggregates. This may explain variations in the values compared to the size ranges in which they were found. The particle sizes determined after measurement in wet dispersion are slightly higher than the sizes determined by measurement in dry dispersion. It shows that no agglomeration occurs, but the particles are swelling in suspension.

11. Validation status

- in house
- ILC

The results of the validation report should be briefly summarized here.

Example: this method is not yet validated/is validated.

12. Literature references

- [1] ISO/TR 21960:2020, Plastics – Environmental aspects – State of knowledge and methodologies. <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100472>

Annexes

Describe which documents are given in the annex

e.g. Datasheet for estimation of measurement uncertainty incl. measurement bias, standard deviation, number of particles, procedure for bias correction

Document change history and approval

Version number	Changes made	Date
1	New document	07/04/2025
2	Format Conversion	
3	Minor Changes	

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